

A STUDY OF READING HABBIT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

In this digital era reading habit of students depend on technology. Every information reaches students with digital media. The students develop reading habit with different media as per their choice. The present study focus on 'Reading Habit of secondary school students. The study reveals that a significant difference was observed between rural and urban secondary school students with respect reading habit scores ($t = -2.5753$, $p < 0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, reading habit scores are significantly higher urban schools as compare to rural secondary school students and A significant difference was observed between joint family and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to reading habit scores ($t = -3.4867$ $p < 0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, reading habit scores are significantly higher nuclear family member as compare to joint family member of secondary schools. It is concluded that teachers and parents should encourage students to read printed materials in terms of book text books, novels, news papers etc which are healthy reading habit.

Keywords —: Compare, Digital, Encourage, Knowledge, Media, Print, Reading

I. INTRODUCTION

The present global education system follows techno-friendly classroom. This digital era made students to learn, speak, read, write through digital media. The present youths talk, does conversation with another person with digital media. The students study their academic work with technically based media. Through different blogs, vlogs, apps, made learning easy. The print media is used very lesser number. The question arises here is how many students using print media to read. Not only academics but also for shake of gaining knowledge, students reads magazines and general knowledge books, reference book, texts books. The present study focus on 'reading habit' of secondary school students.

II. GENESIS OF PROBLEM

The researcher observed at government library that old people were reading news paper. Few students entered in library and started discussion about

books. The print media is good for reading or digital media is good for reading. But librarian shouted at them made them to go outside. The researcher observed that at library all people who were reading they are old people above fifty aged people. No single young fellow present there. The question arises why only old people adopted print media. why not youths? The researcher visited schools and college library. It is observed that only few students adopt print media for reading. Many students follows digital media for reading news, notes, academic texts, novel, etc. The researcher conducted clinical interview with college students regarding their reading habit. The response was that they prefer to read from watsup messages, from blogs, from apps, from internet reading is an easy task for them. But print media like news paper reading, magazine reading, reading novel, reading text book etc were hanging in the world of digital era. It is hot burning problem that every individual

is using internet based reading rather print base reading. The rural area students may not get good books to read or nuclear family students may not get good time to study or they may facing problems so the research minds should think about this problem .So the main question arises here is that why don't study young youth's reading habit with respect to rural and urban and also family type.

III.REVIEWS

1.(Murugan K, 2013) Investigated a study on "Reading habits among users of the public library of Vellore district, Tamil Nadu: a survey". The study of data collected from 120 users by administering questionnaires among them to obtain their attitude towards reading habits and the purpose of the Library Visit in the public library of Vellore district, Tamil Nadu. Indicates the purpose of the reading, language preference, collection form of the library, assistance of the library staff in the use of resources and necessary services to help users meet their information requirements. The findings are that people cannot visit the library regularly due to lack or lack of time, and the literature is read mainly by serious users, and magazines and newspapers are the most common forms preferred by readers.

2.(Mahwish Rabia, 2017) Reading habits determine the academic achievement of students to a large extent. Both reading and academic achievement are interrelated and depend on each other. Students often come from different backgrounds and locations with different levels of academic achievement. Therefore, they differ in the pattern of reading habits. While some students have good reading habits, others tend to exhibit poor reading habits. Academic achievement means how much knowledge the individual has acquired from the school.

3.(WILSON, 2007) In a sample of university students at the Technological University of Tennessee indicates a poor use of newspapers among university students and finds that, on average, participants read a newspaper about 15 minutes, once a week, the literacy practices of family newspapers are strong, while K-12 newspaper exposure and civic interest are moderate. According to the academic, the use and preferences

of other students in the media include the Internet and television, although they qualify the newspapers as more accurate and credible than these sources of information.

4.(Shen, 2006)Conducted a study with the objective of determining the impact of computer technology on the reading habits of university students and concludes that the reading habits of university student's change from paper-based reading to Internet based reading. The findings show that 83.9% of students read the information online every day, while only 31.4% of them read newspapers and 33.1% read magazines on a daily basis.

5.(Kerfoot, 2002) Believed that reading is a process of thinking, evaluating, evaluating, reasoning images and solving problems. Reading is an essential tool for the transfer of knowledge and the habit of reading an academic activity that increases the ability in reading strategies. To know about the world and its environment, a child helps himself by reading books, newspapers and other magazines. Once the child has learned to read and has developed a love for books, he can explore for himself the richness of human experiences and knowledge through reading. Children, who lose the opportunity to get in touch with books in their early stages of life, find it difficult to acquire good reading habits in their years.

6.(Mellon, 1990) He examined leisure reading options for rural adolescents and found that his reasons for leisure reading were entertainment and information acquisition. Magazines and newspapers were the preferred reading materials for teenagers. It has also been shown that informative reading was the main objective of reading adults and that their most popular books are: leased on the subject such as; Adventures, crime, social problems, novels, politics and sports in sequence of classification.

7.(Md. Sohail, 2011) He conducted a survey to study the reading habits of users of the Delhi Public Library, New Delhi. The finding indicates that the purpose of the reading, the language preference, the collection form of the library, the assistance of the library staff in the use of resources and services is necessary to help users meet their requirements. Information. The results also suggest that people cannot visit the library regularly due to lack or lack

of time, and the literature that most users read are magazines and newspapers.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

1. Healthy entertainment: The reading habit provide an experience of joy of reading. The good books are like good friends silently suggest good paths to life.

2. Print media reading is healthy: The print media reading is healthy reading which may not harm eye and brain,ear,heart, the mobiles and digital media seriously harmful.

3. Develops concentration, Memory: The reading habit develops concentration and improves memory and can help to retain information for more time.

4. patient and tolerable: The reading habit improves patience and inculcates listening skills among people.

5. Develops vocabulary: The reading habit develops good vacubalary and literary knowledge and general knowledge about subject which they read.

6. Mental health: The reading habit develops mental peace and reduces stress. It is a stress relieving activity which can makes person mentally healthy.

V. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the reading habit of secondary school students as per their location.

2. To study the reading habits of secondary school students as per their family type

VI. HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis.1: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to reading habit

Hypothesis.2: There is no significant difference between joint family and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to reading habit

VII. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection:
a. Samples: Among all students population only two hundred students studying in secondary school considered as samples. The simple random sampling method was employed to collect data. The students studying in 8th standard are acted as samples. The Belagavi,Koppal,Vijayapura,Kalaburgi districts rural and urban schools were considered for study.

b. Reaserch tool:The ‘Reading Habbit Scale’was constructed with four level of validation process.

Internal consistency was checked. Reliability was verified with Chronbatcha alfa method. The (RHS) Reading Habbit Scale was followed with likert five point scale. The RHS has five indicators 1. News paper reading 2. Magazine reading 3. Literature reading 4. GK book reading 5. Test books/reference reading

c. Stastics: To computa data Mean,SD,T-test were used

A. Data Analysis

Hypothesis.1: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to their reading habit

Table.1: results of t-test between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to reading habits.

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Si gni .
Rural	100	73.24	10.43	-2.5753	0.0019	S
Urban	100	81.72	13.09		<0.05	

A significant difference was observed between rural and urban secondary school students with respect reading habit scores (t=-2.5753, p<0.05) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, reading habit scores are significantly higher urban schools as compare to rural secondary school students

Hypothesis.2: There is no significant difference between joint family and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to their reading habit

Table.2: results of t test between joint family member and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to their reading habit

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Sig ni.
Joint family	80	68.55	9.88	-3.4867	0.0016	S
Nuclear family	120	88.55	12.06		<0.05	

A significant difference was observed between joint family and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to reading habit scores (t= -3.4867 p<0.05) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that,

reading habit scores are significantly higher nuclear family member as compare to joint family member of secondary schools.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND INTEPRETATION

1.A significant difference was observed between rural and urban secondary school students with respect reading habit scores ($t=-2.5753$, $p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, reading habit scores are significantly higher urban schools as compare to rural secondary school students. The urban area students read new papers and magazines and GK books and also they read textbook with the help of print media and responded 'Strongly agree'.It is observed that more than fifty percent of them not has spectacles and they are methally healthy.But The study conducted by Dayang Azimah Abang Yusof ,Tun Abdul Razak Library, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Sarawak Branch on the topic 'Reading Habits Among Students in the Digital Era: Changes of Trends and Behaviours. The findings also found that majority of the students (49%) preferred reading from their mobile phone, whereas others preferred reading from a print book (44%) and reading from a computer (7%). Findings of the study revealed that the rise of information and technology has extensively changes the trends and behaviors of the student's reading habits, which slowly moving away from printed books to online source materials.

2.A significant difference was observed between joint family and nuclear family member of secondary school students with respect to reading habit scores ($t= -3.4867$ $p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, reading habit scores are significantly higher nuclear family member as compare to joint family member of secondary schools. The nuclear family member students shown better performance that they always reads magazines and literature books and text books.

IX.SUGGESTIONS

1.It is suggested that the same study can be conducted any location and any stream of education of the world.

2.In all streams of curriculum reading classes should be reserved. Because reading habbit with print media improves mental health of person.

3.Global youths facing many health issues because of more using print media reading. In future which may lead blind world.

4.It is high time to spread awareness among all people of world that they should take care of their children and advice them to use print based reading.

IX.CONCLUSION

As per above research teachers and parents should encourage students to read printed materials in terms of book text books, novels, news papers etc which are healthy reading habit. Our young generation must develop healthy reading habit.The good reading habit develops healthy future and unhealthy reading habbit like digital base reading causes blind future.So there is a need of urgent solution for this problem. Otherwise the future generation will fall in darkness world without any guidance.

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